

نیادی ماخذ شریعت میں تخفیف کا مقام و حکم

**THE STATUS AND ORDER OF MITIGATION
IN BASIC SOURCES OF SHARIAH****Abdul Majid (ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7133-6853)**

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ABSTRACT

The welfare of human kind in individual and collective live is in believing and following Islamic way of life. Islamic code of life exalt the human kind to new dimensions. It has a code of life for all times and universal, not subservient to time and space. On the contrary, Islamic code of life with all its manifestation is as much work-able and needed today as it was it was in the early glorious period of Islam.

Allah, in all His mercy has made the "Islam" simple, workable with exceptions and relief where ever one feels difficulty, danger or deprivation. Base on the Quran, the Holy Prophet (ﷺ) guided the followers on such matter where exceptions or relief was needed. After the Holy Prophet (ﷺ) the responsibility of guidance was taken out by his companions, after their period the Imams coded all the problems in "fiqh".

Today the human kind, particularly Muslims face new challenges regarding different problems in the matter of practice. This study has established guidance and solutions in the form of exceptions and relief given in Sharia. The hall-mark of it is that Allah and his Prophet (ﷺ) has provided relief.

Keywords: Islamic way of life, Universal code of life, Exceptions, New challenges.

کلیدی الفاظ: اسلامی نظام حیات، عالمی قوانین زندگی، مستثنیات، نئی ترجیحات۔

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7525161